

Yield performance under the rice *yaya* demonstration program in Sri Lanka: a case study

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Launched in 1997, the rice *yaya* (tract) demonstration program aimed to determine how farmers' rice yields could be further improved. The program involves extension activities to promote integrated crop management and the use of good-quality seeds and to provide credit and training facilities in selected locations across several districts in Sri Lanka. This study evaluated the impact of the rice *yaya* demonstration program on rice production. A field investigation was undertaken in one of the dry-zone rice-growing districts of southern Sri Lanka, Hambantota.

Field work was carried out in the irrigated areas of Hambantota District. Two farmer

categories in the tract program, participants and nonparticipants (40 each), were interviewed at the end of the 2001 *yala* (dry) season (Apr-Aug). Current and past yield data were recorded. Table 1 shows the yield performance in the past seasons of both participants and nonparticipants.

During the past four seasons, the average yields obtained by program participants were higher than those of nonparticipants; the yield difference was more than 1.5 t ha⁻¹.

A comparison of the yield performance before and after the program indicated a shift to higher yield categories. In fact, the two upper yield categories (7.23 t ha⁻¹ and above) were represented

by 40% of the farmers after implementation of the program. Furthermore, none of the farmers had yields between 3.09 and 4.12 t ha⁻¹. Before the tract program, only 5% of the farmers were in the two highest yield categories, while 20% were in the lowest category. This implies that 40% of the program participants were in the two upper yield categories, in contrast to only 10% of the nonparticipants.

The study reveals that the extension program has made a positive impact on overall rice yield.

Table 2. Yields obtained by participants and nonparticipants, 2001 *yala*.

Yield range (t ha ⁻¹)	% of participants		% of nonparticipants
	Before program	After program	
3.90–4.12	20	0	0
4.13–5.15	35	10	18
5.16–6.18	5	22	47
6.19–7.22	5	22	47
7.23–8.24	5	35	8
8.25–9.27	0	5	2

Table 1. Yield performance of selected farms in Hambantota District, 1998-2000.

Season ^a	Highest grain yield (participating farms)	Av yield (participating farms)	Av yield (nonparticipating farms)	Yield difference (t ha ⁻¹)
Yala (1998)	7.5	5.9	4.2	1.7
Maha (1998/99)	9.7	5.9	4.0	1.9
Yala (1999)	7.5	5.3	3.2	2.1
Maha (1999/2000)	7.9	5.9	3.2	2.7

^aYala = dry season from April to August. Maha = wet season from October to February.

Agricultural extension and farmer needs for technology

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The accelerated Mahaweli Development Program is a major agricultural development effort for the dry zone of Sri Lanka. Through its agricultural extension

component, innovations were introduced to rice farmers in the area. This study aimed to evaluate how effectively the agricultural extension system has

introduced technologies to meet actual needs of farmers.

This study was carried out in Tambuttegama in the Mahaweli H Zone. One hundred

rice farmers were included in the field investigation. A pretested questionnaire was used to gather data just after the 2001-02 maha season (Apr-May). A scoring procedure was applied to rank farmers' views on technology dissemination. Rank 1 is given seven points and rank 7 is given one point. Table 1 shows the various technologies as ranked by farmers in terms of importance. Sixty-three farmers had identified varietal recommendations as the most important technology disseminated. Sixteen farmers gave the same technology a ranking of 2. The total score for each technology is the sum of the products of the number of farmer-respondents in a rank class multiplied by the corresponding score point.

The technological innovations that have been disseminated were ranked by farmers thus: varieties (1), fertilizer (2), pest and disease control methods (3), irrigation methods (4), weed control methods (5), land preparation methods (6), and transplanting methods (7).

Similarly, farmer needs were also identified using the same ranking procedure. Table 2 shows the ranking of these needs.

The most important need identified by rice farmers is to gain knowledge on organic farming (Table 2). Market information, training, input supply, credit facilities, and business counseling, in that order, were also deemed important.

The study reveals that the technologies disseminated do not match the farmers' needs. It is crucial that extension efforts be reoriented to serve the current needs pointed out by farmers.

Table 1. Farmers' ranking of various technologies in terms of importance.

Technology	Rank ^a							Total ^b score	Final rank
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
Varietal recommendations	63	16	9	3	3	4	2	613	1
Fertilizer recommendations	8	44	16	11	13	4	4	495	2
Pest and disease control methods	7	9	26	32	13	7	6	420	3
Weed control methods	1	9	19	20	22	20	9	351	5
Land preparation methods	3	5	14	20	19	23	16	320	6
Irrigation methods	12	15	9	8	14	28	14	363	4
Transplanting methods	7	2	7	7	16	14	47	247	7

^aRank 1 is given seven points; rank 7 is given one point. ^bSum of products of number of farmer-respondents multiplied by corresponding score point.

Table 2. Farmers' ranking of actual needs.

Need	Rank ^a						Total ^b score	Final rank
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Loan/credit	7	8	5	14	42	24	252	5
Knowledge on organic farming	47	24	13	12	3	1	497	1
Market information	12	26	37	17	7	1	416	2
Training	9	28	32	21	8	2	403	3
Input supply	24	8	9	28	24	7	359	4
Business counseling	0	3	4	9	16	68	158	6

^aRank 1 is given six points; rank 6 is given one point. ^bSum of products of number of farmer-respondents multiplied by corresponding score point.

Advance estimation of rice production in India using weather indices

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Estimation of crop production from area and yield estimates based on sample surveys and crop-cutting experiments, an approach currently being followed in India, can give final estimates only after the crops are actually harvested. However, various

policy decisions related to pricing, marketing, export/import, distribution, etc., necessitate the use of advance estimates. A simple model based on weather indices can be used to obtain accurate estimates of annual rice production even before the crop

is harvested.

Crop production in India largely depends on the summer monsoon (June to September), which provides about 80–90% of annual rainfall in most parts of the country. The summer monsoon rainfall is the main source of